

Course: ANTH 239
Forensic Anthropology & Bioarchaeology
Class Time: Tues/Thurs 10:30–11:45 AM
Instructor: Dr Jess Beck
Email: jessicabeck@vassar.edu
Office Hours: Thursday, 12:30–2:30

Forensic anthropologists analyze human skeletal remains from medico-legal contexts and bioarchaeologists analyze human skeletal remains from archaeological sites. Both fields use methods derived from biological anthropology. This course introduces students to the basic methods of these disciplines, including assessing the age, sex, ancestry, and stature of an individual using their bones. Recognition of skeletal anomalies can also reveal past health conditions and the cause and manner of death. This course will also introduce the ongoing disciplinary debate concerning the ethical implications of using skeletal remains to assess ancestry within forensic anthropology. The final project for this course will involve reconstructing the biological profile for an individual of unknown origin. ANTH 229—Skeletal Anatomy is a prerequisite for this course.

*“Skeleton Contemplating a Skull,”
Andreas Vesalius (1543).*

Learning Objectives

By the end of the course students will have experience:

- Differentiating human and non-human bones
- Estimate age, sex, ancestry, and stature from human remains
- Understanding the history of ancestry estimation in forensic anthropology
- Estimating how many individuals are represented by a given set of remains
- Writing and reading biological profile reports

Class Behavior

This class includes handling real human bones and looking at images of dead bodies. All students are expected to maintain high levels of professionalism in this course, which includes respect for the dead and for each other. You may not take personal photos of the real human remains. You may not handle food or drink while working with the remains. Any disrespectful behaviors will result in a penalty on your overall course grade and may result in removal from the course.

Readings

Students must purchase their own copy of the following textbook so that it can be used in class. 2nd edition or 3rd edition are both acceptable. Any additional readings will be posted on Moodle or provided as paper copies.

Burns, Karen Ramey
2012 *Forensic Anthropology Training Manual*. 3rd Edition. Pearson, Boston.

Grading

Your grade in this course will be based on four primary components:

Engagement (20%)	Quizzes (20%)
Exam (30%)	Biological Profile Group Project (30%)

Final course grades will be assigned using a 100-point scale. Vassar does not assign a grade of A+; an “A” grade is ≥ 95 points. A failing grade is ≤ 62 points. Grades will be rounded up or down to the nearest integer.

A- = 90–94

B+ = 87–89

B = 83–86

B- = 80–82

C+ = 77–79

C = 73–76, etc., etc.

COVID-19 NOTE: I recognize that we are living through a global pandemic and that as a result there may be times during the semester when you need to quarantine or miss a class for COVID-related reasons. I will be as flexible as possible when making accommodations. If you require accommodations for COVID-related reasons, please let me know as soon as possible and we will find a way for you to make up the work.

Schedule of Quizzes, Exams & Notebook Due Date

Assignment	Date
Quiz 1: Estimating Age	Tuesday, April 26
Quiz 2: Assessing Sex	Tuesday, May 4
Quiz 3: Assessing Ancestry & Stature	Tuesday, May 11
Quiz 4: Evaluating Taphonomy & Trauma, Estimating MNI	Tuesday, May 18
Exam	Thursday, May 20
Biological Profile Due	Monday, May 24

Grading Structure

Engagement (20%): A weekly attendance sheet will circulate that in-person students are required to sign. It is your responsibility to sign the attendance sheet—if you are not able to do so at the beginning of class, you are responsible for asking for the attendance sheet at the end of class. However, simply showing up is not sufficient to achieve the full 20%. Active demonstration that you are engaged with the course material, including participating in labs, contributing to class discussion, and diligently working on your Biological Profile Group Project will also be factored into this grade.

Quizzes (20%): There are four quizzes which will occur on the first meeting of the week and will take approximately 15 minutes of class time. Quizzes are worth 5% each. These weekly quizzes will cover material learned the preceding week and will range in structure from

multiple choice, feature identification, and practical applications of knowledge learned during the course. Treat these quizzes as practice for your practical exam—they are an opportunity for you to test your skills under time pressure and identify areas that you need to work on.

Exam (30%): There will be one exam in this course; the exam will incorporate a variety of question formats, potentially including visual identification, hands-on analysis, multiple choice, written responses, and other formats. The exam is worth 30%.

Biological Group Profile (30%): You will be assigned a small group and tasked with working together to produce a biological profile of an individual or individuals of unknown origin. A set of guidelines for this assignment will be distributed by the third week of class.

Office Hours

Office hours will be held on Zoom from 12:30–2:30 every Thursday, with additional Zoom office hours scheduled by appointment for students who cannot make that time slot. To attend office hours, please make an appointment on my [Google Calendar](#) so that multiple students are not trying to meet with me simultaneously. A link to the Google Appointments page for office hours is posted on Moodle. Appointment slots will be for 20-minute increments. If you think that you will need more time to discuss a particular issue, please email me in advance.

Plagiarism Policy

In this course you will collaborate with other students during activities and participate in group discussions where other students' ideas will not doubt affect your own. However, in your own worksheets and written assignments, do not submit someone else's words or ideas as your own. Plagiarism will result in a zero on the offending assignment and more egregious cases will incur stronger penalties in accordance with Vassar academic policy. You can read the guidelines on Integrity of Academic Work in the Vassar College Regulations available online here: <https://deanofthecollege.vassar.edu/documents/college-regulations/VassarCollegeRegulations.pdf>

Accessibility Accommodations

If you have a condition that requires special accommodations, please have it documented by the Office for Accessibility and Educational Opportunity and provide me with a copy of your AEO accommodation letter before your accommodations are needed.

Title IX Responsibilities

All Vassar faculty members are “responsible employees;” if you inform a member of the faculty about a situation involving sexual harassment, sexual assault, relationship abuse, or stalking, they must share that information with the Title IX Coordinator. After a notification, the Title IX office will only provide outreach by email, meaning that you will control how your case will be handled—you do not have to read or reply to the email. It is entirely your decision whether or not to pursue a formal complaint.

Virtual Resources

Consult your ANTH 229 syllabus for a list of virtual resources and online repositories of human anatomy.

Class Schedule and Reading List

The readings assigned for a particular day should be read **before** that day, to ensure that you are prepared for the discussion or activities. I reserve the right to change the readings, activities, and discussion if I believe such a change is pertinent to our safety and/or the direction of the course. Please note that you will be reading many sections of osteology and anatomy reference manuals, rather than complete chapters. This is intended to familiarize you with some of the key volumes most frequently used by bioarchaeologists and forensic anthropologists.

Week 1: Forensic Anthropology & Bioarchaeology + Estimating Subadult Age (April 13–15)

Tuesday, April 13

Topic: Forensic Anthropology & Bioarchaeology

Optional Reading(s): Burns, Chapter 1: Introduction to Forensic Anthropology

Thursday, April 15

Topic: Estimating Subadult Age

Reading(s): Scheuer and Black 2004, Chapter 1 + In Burns:

- Familiarize yourself with the origin and growth sections for major long bones
- Read Chapter 11: Section on *Dental Aging*

Week 2: Estimating Adult Age + Age Estimation Lab (April 20–22)

Tuesday, April 20

Topic: Estimating Adult Age

Reading(s): Focus on the following sections from Burns:

- Chapter 3: The Skull—*Age Changes in the Skull*
- Chapter 4: The Shoulder Girdle and Thorax—Sections on aging the clavicle + ribs
- Chapter 5: The Vertebral Column—*The Aging Vertebral Body*
- Chapter 8: The Pelvis—*Age Changes in the Pelvis*

Thursday, April 22

Topic: Age Estimation Lab

Reading(s): Read the following sections in Buikstra & Ubelaker 1994:

- Chapter 3: Documentation of Age Changes (pp. 21–38)
- Chapter 4: Immature Remains: Maturation and Measurement (pp. 39–43)
- Chapter 5: Dental Data Collection I (pp. 47–53)

Week 3: Assessing Sex + Sex Estimation Lab (April 27–29)

Tuesday, April 27

QUIZ 1: Estimating Age

Reading(s): Stone 2012 + Focus on the following sections from Burns:

- Chapter 3: The Skull and Hyoid—*Sex Differences in the Skull*

- Chapter 8: The Pelvis—*Sexual Differences*
- Chapter 9: The Leg—Sections on sex differences in the femur + tibia

Thursday, April 29

Topic: Sex Estimation Lab

Reading(s): White and Folkens 2005, Chapter 19: Determination of Sex (pp.386–398).

Week 4: Assessing Ancestry & Stature + Taphonomy, Trauma & MNI (May 4–6)
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Tuesday, May 4

QUIZ 2: Estimating Sex

Reading(s): Burns, Chapter 3 (read section *Racial Analysis of the Skull; Anthropometry*); Sauer 1992; DiGangi & Bethard 2020; White and Folkens 2005, Chapter 19: Estimation of Stature + Estimation of Ancestry (pp. 398–404).

Thursday, May 6

Topic: Taphonomy, Trauma, and MNI Lecture

Reading(s): Burns, Chapter 14: Field Methods; Beck et al. 2015; Dirkmaat and Cabo 2016

Week 5: Ancestry, Stature, Taphonomy, Trauma & MNI Lab + Class Project Day (May 11–13)
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Tuesday, May 11

QUIZ 3: Ancestry & Stature

Topic: Ancestry, Stature, Taphonomy, Trauma & MNI Lab

Thursday, May 13

Topic: Class Project Day

Week 6: Class Project Day + Exam (May 18–20)
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Tuesday, May 18

QUIZ 4: Evaluating Taphonomy and Trauma, Estimating MNI

CLASS PROJECT DAY

Reading: Burns, Chapter 13: Laboratory Analysis

Thursday, May 20

EXAM

Reading List

Beck, J., I. Ostericher, G. Sollish & J. De León. (2015). Animal scavenging and scattering and the implications for documenting the deaths of undocumented border crossers in the Sonoran Desert. *Journal of Forensic Sciences* 60(S1): S11–S20. doi: 10.1111/1556-4029.12597.

Buikstra, J. E., & D.H. Ubelaker (Eds.). (1994). *Standards for data collection from human skeletal remains*. Arkansas Archaeological Survey Research Series No. 44. Arkansas Archaeological Survey.

DiGangi, E.A., & J. D. Bethard. (2021). Uncloaking a lost cause: Decolonizing ancestry estimation in the United States. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 2021:1–15. DOI:10.1002/ajpa.24212.

Dirkmaat, D.C., & L. L. Cabo. (2016). Forensic archaeology and forensic taphonomy: Basic considerations on how to properly process and interpret the outdoor forensic scene. *Academic Forensic Pathology International* 6(3):439–454. DOI: 10.23907/2016.045

Sauer, N. J. (1992). Forensic anthropology and the concept of race: If races don't exist, why are forensic anthropologists so good at identifying them? *Social Science and Medicine* 34(2):107–111. DOI:10.1016/0277-9536(92)90086-6.

Scheuer, L., & Black, S. (2004). *The juvenile skeleton*. Academic Press.

Stone, P. K. (2012). A bioarchaeology of sex and gender: What is the difference and why is it important? *The SAA Archaeological Record* 12(2),38–40.

White, T. D., & Folkens. P.A. (2005). *The human bone manual*. Academic Press.